

Insight into bio-methanol production and *in silico* elucidation of particulate methane monooxygenase enzyme from methanogens

Authors: Kumudinee Shivankar, Dr. Shreya Anand

Abstract

The escalating environmental repercussions of fossil fuel combustion, particularly greenhouse gas emissions, in conjunction with the surging global energy demand, have spurred the quest for alternative energy sources. Methanol has emerged as a pivotal energy substitute due to its high octane rating and associated advantages such as diminished flammability, superior performance, and reduced emissions. Conventionally, bio-methanol production involves gasification and pyrolysis processes, with gasification yielding superior outcomes. To render gasification economically viable, an array of renewable inputs, encompassing biomass residues and byproducts from diverse sectors like biogas from landfills, wastewater, solid waste processing, black liquor from the pulp and paper domain, and glycerin, can be harnessed post-appropriate pretreatment to ensure heightened yield. The underlying mechanism for bio-methanol synthesis pivots on fermentation, leveraging the biotransformation prowess of prokaryotic proteobacteria methanotrophs to convert methane into methanol. This conversion is orchestrated by the enzyme methane monooxygenase (MMO), which exists in two distinct forms within methanotrophs: particulate (pMMO), associated with membranes, and soluble (sMMO). Despite their shared catalytic aptitude for methane-to-methanol oxidation, these enzymes exhibit dissimilarities in their amino acid sequences and metal cofactor requisites. Remarkably, both enzymes have independently evolved to address the same molecular challenge, coexisting within the same bacterial milieu. This study delves into the comprehensive elucidation of the particulate methane monooxygenase enzyme (EC 1.14.18.3) through an *in silico* approach. It encompasses enzyme characterization, estimation of physicochemical and functional attributes via tools like ProtParam and FASTA, determination of secondary structure using SOPMA, and execution of molecular docking through Swiss-Model and Swiss-Dock. For the docking analysis, two variants of pMMO were selected—*Methylococcus capsulatus* (Bath) [PDB ID: 1YEW/7t4o] and *Methylosinus trichosporium* OB3b [PDB ID: 3CHX]—with Zinc and Copper ions as ligands, shedding light on their roles as inducers or inhibitors for both enzyme forms.

Keywords - Bio-methanol, Particulate Methane Monooxygenase (pMMO), Methanotrophs, etc.

1. Introduction

With the growing human population, global energy needs are increasing exponentially ^[1]. Although primary energy resources are conventional fossil fuels, their combustion has resulted in a strong negative environmental impact ^[2]. To mitigate this, a non-conventional energy source such as bio-methanol with comparative precedence is required to mitigate the negative environmental impact. Bio-methanol is a light, colorless, volatile, flammable liquid, water-soluble, and biodegradable at ambient conditions. It is potentially used in fuel cell vehicles as it can completely decompose into CO₂ and water in the presence of steam. M85, which is a mixture of 85% methanol and 15% gasoline, can be used in existing vehicles without major technical modifications to the existing vehicle ^[3]. A significant part of methanol is derived from fossil fuels; approximately 65% is produced by reforming natural gas, and coal gasification gives 35% of the total, while renewable sources contribute only <1% as the production cost of bio-methanol is estimated between 1.5 and 4 times higher than the cost of natural gas-based methanol^[4-5]. The main factors deciding the total production cost of bio-methanol are feedstock selection and their prices, plant set-up, and local conditions ^[5].

With rising atmospheric concentrations, methane, the simplest hydrocarbon and primary component of natural gas, is a potent greenhouse gas (GHG). Methane is a significant contributor to global warming because, despite making up only 10% of the atmosphere's greenhouse gases, it is 25 times more potent than carbon dioxide (CO₂) as a GHG ^[6]. All aerobic methanotrophic bacteria use the enzyme MMO to oxidize methane to methanol with oxygen, regardless of their metabolic differences ^[7]. Through several steps and intermediaries, MMO must catalyze the cleavage of two essential chemical bonds to enable methane oxidation in methanotrophs: methane's C-H bond and dioxygen bond ^[8]. Methanol (CH₃OH) is the simplest of the alcohol family but one of the largest commodities of energy and the chemical industry. After a reasonable pretreatment to ensure a higher yield, bio-methanol can be produced from waste biomass such as agro-waste, forest litter, and urban organic waste using various thermochemical and biochemical processes ^[9]. Bio-methanol can be produced by fermenting or distilling starch-rich crops, reportedly produced methanol from crop residues, trees, and forages. Rice bran produced the most methanol from the various tested biomasses (55%) ^[10].

Methanotrophs are prokaryotes that belong to the Proteobacteria family. They are involved in the natural carbon cycle and the metabolism of CH₄ for biomass production, resulting in the release of carbon dioxide (CO₂) as a byproduct of oxidation ^[11]. The enzyme responsible for the one-step conversion of CH₄ into methanol is called methane monooxygenase (MMO). Methanol is then broken down by methanol dehydrogenase (MDH) into formaldehyde, which is then broken down by formaldehyde dehydrogenase into formate. Formate dehydrogenase finally breaks down formate, releasing CO₂ ^[12]. Particulate methane monooxygenase (pMMO) is an integral membrane metalloenzyme that oxidizes methane to methanol in methanotrophic bacteria ^[13]. Studying the biochemistry and structure of pMMO, with an emphasis on samples from *Methylococcus capsulatus* (Bath) and *Methylosinus trichosporium* OB3b, holds significant potential for improving the efficiency of bio-methanol production through the utilization of sustainable sources and more economical raw materials. Methanotrophs can have two MMOs: particulate (pMMO: associated with membranes) and soluble (sMMO). Based on these types of MMOs they contain, methanotrophs are broadly divided into three categories (I, II, and X). Methanotrophs of type I only produce pMMO. Both pMMO and sMMO are produced by Type II methanotrophs. Type II methanotrophs can absorb CH₄ through the serine cycle, and type X shares some characteristics with Types I and II. One example of a Type X methanotroph is *Methylococcus capsulatus* ^[14]. There is much more to understand about the catalytic cycle of pMMO; however, rather than involving radical or cation intermediates, the retention of the stereochemistry observed during oxygenation of cryptically chiral alkanes strongly suggests a concerted 187 mechanism of C-H bond breakage ^[15]. Accomplishing the creation of synthetic compounds by applying natural methanotrophs has not been acknowledged despite the broad exploration exercises. However, many researchers have aimed to establish heterologous MMO production to achieve synthetic methanotrophy rather than engineering methanotrophs. As recently referenced, pMMO is challenging to express actively heterologously because of its account toxicity and membrane-bound nature. Methanotrophs' pMMO is expressed under high copper-to-biomass ratio conditions during growth ^[16]. Methanotrophs without sMMO, such as *Methylomicrobium album* BG8 or *Methylocystis parvus* OBBP, do not grow well when all trace amounts of copper ions are removed from the growth medium ^[17]. pMMO is well-established as a copper-containing enzyme^[18]. Still, its instability during purification has made it difficult to reach a consensus about its composition and catalytic properties, even though it appears responsible for most of the methane oxidation catalyzed by methanotrophic bacteria in the environment ^[18].

This paper aims to elucidate and compare the characteristics of the pMMO enzyme from different bacteria, *Methylococcus capsulatus str.* [Bath], uncultured bacteria and *Methylosinus trichosporium* OB3b using *In silico* methods for estimating physicochemical and functional properties through ProtParam and SOPMA represented a secondary structure of enzyme along with this Swiss Dock tool used for molecular docking.

In silico, the characterization of pMMO is carried out using various bioinformatics tools and molecular docking. The study uses a previous understanding of the pMMO enzyme from the available scientific literature. The primary and secondary structures of the enzyme were observed using SOPMA and ProtParam and compared. Conformational changes are visualized with the help of ChimeraX and DiscoveryStudio 2021, and molecular docking is performed using the Swiss model/dock.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Physiochemical and functional characterization

The amino acid sequences of particulate methane monooxygenase (pMMO) were obtained by accessing the NCBI Protein Database and the Expert Protein Analysis System (EXPASY) proteomic server. The sequences were obtained for uncultured bacteria and the particulate methane monooxygenase subunit *Methylococcus capsulatus str.* [Bath], and a comparative analysis of the results was performed. Using the ProtParam tool of Expasy, molecular weight, theoretical isoelectric point (pI value), the total number of negatively and positively charged residues, extinction coefficients, instability index, and aliphatic index were computed.

Secondary structural features were predicted using the self-optimized alignment (SOPMA) prediction method. BLASTp was performed using the FASTA sequence from NCBI (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) for methane monooxygenase subunit *Methylococcus capsulatus str.* [Bath].

2.2. Modelling and validation of enzymes

The structure of pMMO was unavailable in Protein Data Bank and thus was modeled using the Swiss Model (<https://swissmodel.expasy.org/interactive>). Swiss Model is an online tool that follows the algorithm of homology modeling. It involves a template to model the structure. The most suitable template is selected from the list of templates based on the similarity percentage and the provided coverage area. The three-dimensional (3D) structures were visualized using software tools like ChimeraX and Discovery Studio.

3. Result and discussion

By employing the SOPMA tool, the analysis of the pMMO sequence extracted from uncultured bacteria and the pMMO subunit derived from *Methylococcus capsulatus str. Bath* has led to the graphical depiction of their respective secondary structures, encompassing the constituent amino acids. The secondary structure predicted using SOPMA is shown in Table 1. The structural insights for the pMMO sequence from uncultured bacteria are shown in Figure 1a, and for the pMMO subunit originating from *Methylococcus capsulatus str. [Bath.]* are shown in Figure 1b.

Figure 1: SOPMA graphical representation for secondary structures in the pMMO sequence from (a) uncultured bacteria (b) *Methylococcus capsulatus str. [Bath.]*.

Table 1: Secondary structure prediction of pMMO sequence

Secondary Structures	Uncultured bacteria (%)	<i>Methylococcus capsulatus str.</i> (%)
Alpha helices (Hh)	42.64	56.92
3 ₁₀ helices (Gg)	0.00	0.00
Pi helix (Ii)	0.00	0.00
Beta bridge (Bb)	0.00	0.00
Extended strand (Ee)	15.50	16.15
Beta turn (Tt)	6.20	3.46
Bend region (Ss)	0.00	0.00
Random coil (Cc)	35.66	23.46

The amino acids for pMMOs in uncultured bacteria and *Methylococcus capsulatus str.* were obtained from the ProtParam tool (Figure 2). The analysis of amino acid composition revealed that leucine exhibited the highest proportion in both variants of particulate methane monooxygenase (pMMO). Conversely, the content of phenylalanine, proline, threonine, tyrosine, and pyrrolysine was moderately elevated in the pMMO subunit originating from *Methylococcus capsulatus* in comparison to the pMMO derived from uncultured bacterial sources.

Figure 2: Graphical representation of amino acids associated with pMMO of uncultured bacteria and pMMO subunit of *Methylococcus capsulatus* obtained by using the ProtParam tool

The physicochemical properties of the sequence were computed using the ProtParam tool. (Table 2). The amino acid sequence analysis from uncultured bacteria's pMMO revealed a calculated molecular weight of 14797.81 and a theoretical isoelectric point (pI) of 7.77. The total count of negatively charged residues (Asp + Glu) was 3, while positively charged residues amounted to 4. Considering N-terminal Thr (Threonine), the estimated half-life was 7.2 hours in mammalian reticulocytes in vitro, 27.2 hours in yeast in vivo, and 17.2 hours in *E. coli* in vivo. The instability index (II) was calculated as 39.76, classifying the protein as stable. The aliphatic index was also determined to be 86.28, with a Grand average of hydropathicity (GRAVY) of 0.725.

The methane monooxygenase subunit *Methylococcus capsulatus str.* [Bath] showed a molecular weight of 29889.62 and a theoretical pI 5.20, comprising 260 amino acids. The total number of negatively charged residues (Asp + Glu) was 22, while positively charged residues

numbered 15. Considering N-terminal Met (Methionine), the estimated half-life was 30 hours in mammalian reticulocytes in vitro, 50 hours in yeast in vivo, and 40 hours in *E. coli* in vivo. The calculated instability index (II) was 39.91, implying protein stability. The aliphatic index was determined to be 99.12, accompanied by a Grand average of hydropathicity (GRAVY) of 0.412.

Table 2: Physiochemical details of pMMO in uncultured bacteria and *Methylococcus capsulatus str. [Bath]* obtained from the ProtParam tool

Properties	Uncultured bacteria	<i>Methylococcus capsulatus str.</i>
Molecular weight	14797.81	29889.62
Theoretical pI	7.77	5.20
Extinction coefficients	44460 M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	102330 M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹
Instability index (II)	39.76	39.91
Aliphatic index	86.28	99.12
GRAVY	0.725	0.412

The structural modeling was performed for the methane monooxygenase subunit of *Methylococcus capsulatus str. [Bath]*. The SWISS-Model template library was searched for methane monooxygenase (pMMO) of *Methylococcus capsulatus* (PDB ID: 1YEW/7t4o) (Figure 3). These structures were utilized along with Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions as ligands. Subsequently, molecular docking and thermodynamic analysis were conducted utilizing the web-based Swissdock program (<https://www.swissdock.ch/docking>). The Swiss dock platform facilitated the prediction of therapeutic molecular interactions involving the pMMO structures (7t4o and 3CHX) and the ligands above (Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺).

Figure 3: Schematic representation of particulate methane monooxygenase subunit [*Methylococcus capsulatus* str. Bath].

The comprehensive findings of this study infer that pMMO comprises three polypeptides of approximately 49, 27, and 22 kDa. The 27 kDa subunit is the probable active site, substantiated by its affinity for acetylene inhibitor. Notably, eight distinct pMMO proteins have been successfully crystallized, yielding their corresponding crystal structures accessible in the Protein Data Bank (PDB). These structures unveil an active site, prominently featuring copper coordination, positioned at the N-terminus of the β chain. This active site is coordinated by a pair of histidines from an HXH motif and an N-terminal histidine from PmoB1 or PmoB2, acting as ligands ^[19]. The multicopy genes *pmoA*, *pmoB*, and *pmoC* govern the synthesis of the respective 49, 27, and 22-kDa pMMO components and these genes respond to a high copper-to-biomass ratio. Noteworthy variations in copper equivalents per alpha beta gamma protomer have been observed across active pMMO preparations, ranging from 2 to 15 equivalents ^[20]. The *pmoB* subunit, constituting two periplasmic domains connected by two transmembrane helices, unveils distinctive characteristics ^[21]. In the pMMO from *Methylococcus capsulatus* (*Bath*), these soluble domains encompass two copper sites, modeled as mono-copper and dicopper sites ^[22]. Intriguingly, a correlation between copper content in methanotroph membranes and pMMO activity has been observed, with Cu^{2+} ions demonstrating the capacity to stimulate pMMO activity in vitro ^[23]. Structurally, the pMMO from *Methylococcus capsulatus* (*Bath*) reveals three distinct metal centers, including two cupredoxin domains with copper coordination sites ^[24,25]. Additionally, zinc's inhibitory effect on pMMO activity is recognized, and studies on pMMO from *Methylococcus capsulatus* (*Bath*)

indicate zinc inhibition occurring at two separate locations distinct from the copper active site [26, 27].

A significant challenge in pMMO purification is solubilization without causing irreversible activity loss [28, 29]. The use of dodecyl-13-D-maltese for solubilization, discovered in 1989, demonstrated reversibility through restoring activity upon phospholipid re-addition [30]. Notably, dodecyl-13-D-maltese has been foundational in recent pMMO studies due to its effectiveness in solubilization [30].

While investigations suggest copper's pivotal role in pMMO's function, the precise molecular components involved in electron transport from NADH to the active site remain contentious [31]. The existence of an electron transport system, potentially involving duroquinol, has been postulated [32].

As renewable energy sources like wind and solar power become more prevalent, pMMO-driven bio-methanol production could serve as a means to store excess energy in the form of methanol, enabling its use as a renewable fuel when needed [33]. Many industries and countries strive to meet sustainability goals and reduce carbon emissions [34]. Integrating pMMO-based bio-methanol production into industrial processes aligns with these objectives, providing a greener and more sustainable approach to energy and chemical production [35].

In summary, pMMO research for bio-methanol production offers a promising avenue to address environmental, energy, and economic challenges by converting methane, a potent greenhouse gas, into a valuable and versatile fuel and feedstock [36]. It could contribute significantly to the transition towards a more sustainable, low-carbon future [37].

Numerous intriguing questions linger concerning methanotrophs and their crucial enzyme MMO. These encompass the prevalence of sMMO-only methanotrophs, the phylogenetic relationship between pMMO and AMO, the cellular localization, assembly, copper uptake and sequestration mechanisms, electron donor types, methane activation, and the regulatory control of sMMO and pMMO expression. Furthermore, delving into the genome of *Methylococcus capsulatus* holds promise for advancing our understanding of methanotrophic regulation and proteomics.

4. Conclusion

In the realm of methanotrophic organisms, where the expression of either particulate methane monooxygenase (pMMO) or soluble methane monooxygenase (sMMO) can occur, the induction of pMMO is prompted by an elevated copper-to-biomass ratio within the culture

milieu. Notably, the intracytoplasmic membrane is exclusively generated during periods of high-copper growth in methanotrophic bacteria harboring pMMO.

Methane-oxidizing bacteria play a pivotal role in mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and hold promise for diverse applications in biomanufacturing. Central to their primary metabolism is the particulate methane monooxygenase enzyme (pMMO) within intracytoplasmic membranes (ICMs) induced by copper availability. Past explorations of pMMO have predominantly focused on a specific biological arrangement—a trimeric form with a mass of around 300 kDa, composed of subunits PmoA, PmoB, and PmoC. Valuable insights into subunit folds, potential copper active site locations, and transmembrane regions have been gleaned by scrutinizing the crystal structures of pMMO from distinct methanotrophs. A conserved transmembrane region has been identified among these structures. Notably, the active site of pMMO, depending on the analyzed structures, can harbor one or two copper ions. Intriguingly, the pMMO structure derived from *Methylococcus (Mcc.) capsulatus (Bath)* showcases an additional mono-copper site within the pmoB subunit.

Moreover, the active site of the γ chain subunit has shown versatility in accommodating either copper or zinc, contingent on crystallization conditions. Our investigations have unveiled substantial conservation of residues implicated in catalytic reactions. In contrast, there are discernible differences in physicochemical attributes of catalytic domain sites across chains. Furthermore, disparities in the surfaces of Cu and Zn-binding sites within pMMO β chains have been identified. Additionally, the protein topology of the pMMO α , β , and γ chains exhibit variations in alpha-helix and beta-strand counts, leading to distinct positioning and quantity of signal and cytoplasmic peptides within the pMMO protein sequence.

Several intriguing inquiries persist in the context of methanotrophs and their pivotal enzyme MMO. For instance, the reasons underpinning the presence of exclusively sMMO in a subset of methanotrophs. The potential advantages associated with such a configuration warrant comprehensive investigation. The phylogenetic interrelation between pMMO and AMO and the rationale behind the existence of two distinct gene arrangements for these enzymes merits elucidation, along with a deeper understanding of their precise intracellular localization. The intricate assembly process of pMMO, encompassing mechanisms of copper acquisition and sequestration, electron donor preferences, and the intricacies of methane activation, offer fertile ground for further exploration. Essential to our comprehension is delineating the molecular mechanisms orchestrating the controlled expression of both sMMO and pMMO.

Additionally, the culmination of our understanding would be bolstered by the genomic sequencing of *Methylococcus capsulatus*, providing a solid foundation for studies encompassing methanotrophic regulation and proteomics. The enigmatic aspects of zinc's inhibitory role in pMMO function, encompassing details of zinc binding and the inhibition mechanism, invite further investigation. Furthermore, the intricate relationship between metal binding sites and catalytic activity in pMMO, as observed in the distinct metal centers of *Methylococcus capsulatus* pMMO, adds to the multifaceted nature of these enzymes. Given the complexity of these systems, there remains a wealth of opportunities for future research aimed at unraveling their intricacies.

References

1. Nocera, D. G. (2006). On the future of global energy. *Daedalus*, 135(4), 112-115
2. Adebayo, T. S. (2022). Environmental consequences of fossil fuel in Spain amidst renewable energy consumption: a new insight from the wavelet-based Granger causality approach. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, 29(7), 579-592.
3. Prasad, B. N., Pandey, J. K., & Kumar, G. N. (2020). Impact of changing compression ratio on engine characteristics of an SI engine fueled with equi-volume blend of methanol and gasoline. *Energy*, 191, 116605.
4. Methanotrophic Bacteria RICHARD S. HANSON¹ * AND THOMAS E. HANSON²
Department of Microbiology, University of Minnesota, Minneapolis, Minnesota 55455,¹ and Section of Microbiology, University of California, Davis, Davis, California 95616.
5. Shamsul, N. S., Kamarudin, S. K., Rahman, N. A., & Kofli, N. T. (2014). An overview on the production of bio-methanol as potential renewable energy. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 33, 578-588.
6. Howarth, R. W., Santoro, R., & Ingraffea, A. (2011). Methane and the greenhouse-gas footprint of natural gas from shale formations: A letter. *Climatic change*, 106, 679-690.
7. Cui, J. R., Hua, S. F., Li, S. B., Niu, J. Z., Xia, C. G., Xin, J. Y., & Zhu, L. M. (2004). Biosynthesis of Methanol from CO sub (2) and CH sub (4) by Methanotrophic Bacteria. *Biotechnology*, 3, 67-71.
8. Patel, S. K., Mardina, P., Kim, S. Y., Lee, J. K., & Kim, I. W. (2016). Biological

- methanol production by a type II methanotroph *Methylocystis bryophila*. *Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 26(4), 717-724.
9. Demirbas, A. (2008). Biomethanol production from organic waste materials. *Energy Sources, Part A*, 30(6), 565-572.
 10. Patel, S. K., Kalia, V. C., & Lee, J. K. (2023). Integration of biogas derived from dark fermentation and anaerobic digestion of biowaste to enhance methanol production by methanotrophs. *Bioresource Technology*, 369, 128427.
 11. Kamachi, T., & Okura, I. (2018). Methanol biosynthesis using methanotrophs. *Methane biocatalysis: Paving the way to sustainability*, 169-182
 12. SMITH, D. D. S., & DALTON, H. (1989). Solubilisation of methane monooxygenase from *Methylococcus capsulatus* (Bath). *European journal of biochemistry*, 182(3), 667-671.
 13. Kim, H. J., Huh, J., Kwon, Y. W., Park, D., Yu, Y., Jang, Y. E., ... & Lee, J. (2019). Biological conversion of methane to methanol through genetic reassembly of native catalytic domains. *Nature Catalysis*, 2(4), 342-353.
 14. Hanson, R. S., & Hanson, T. E. (1996). Methanotrophic bacteria. *Microbiological reviews*, 60(2), 439-471.
 15. Banerjee, R., Proshlyakov, Y., Lipscomb, J. D., & Proshlyakov, D. A. (2015). Structure of the key species in the enzymatic oxidation of methane to methanol. *Nature*, 518(7539), 431-434.
 16. Murrell, J. C., McDonald, I. R., & Gilbert, B. (2000). Regulation of expression of methane monooxygenases by copper ions. *Trends in microbiology*, 8(5), 221-225.
 17. Nguyen, H. H., Shiemke, A. K., Jacobs, S. J., Hales, B. J., Lidstrom, M. E., & Chan, S. I. (1994). The nature of the copper ions in the membranes containing the particulate methane monooxygenase from *Methylococcus capsulatus* (Bath). *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 269(21), 14995-15005.
 18. Wang, V. C. C., Maji, S., Chen, P. P. Y., Lee, H. K., Yu, S. S. F., & Chan, S. I. (2017). Alkane oxidation: methane monooxygenases, related enzymes, and their biomimetics. *Chemical reviews*, 117(13), 8574-8621.
 19. Lieberman, R. L., & Rosenzweig, A. C. (2005). Crystal structure of a membrane-bound metalloenzyme that catalyses the biological oxidation of methane. *Nature*, 434(7030), 177-182.
 20. Hakemian, A. S., & Rosenzweig, A. C. (2007). The biochemistry of methane oxidation. *Annu. Rev. Biochem.*, 76, 223-241.

21. Lu, Y. J., Hung, M. C., Chang, B. T. A., Lee, T. L., Lin, Z. H., Tsai, I. K., ... & Yu, S. S. F. (2019). The PmoB subunit of particulate methane monooxygenase (pMMO) in *Methylococcus capsulatus* (Bath): The CuI sponge and its function. *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, 196, 110691.
22. Himes, R. A., & Karlin, K. D. (2009). Copper–dioxygen complex mediated C–H bond oxygenation: relevance for particulate methane monooxygenase (pMMO). *Current opinion in chemical biology*, 13(1), 119-131.
23. Semrau, J. D., Zolanz, D., Lindstrom, M. E., & Chan, S. I. (1995). The role of copper in the pMMO of *Methylococcus capsulatus* Bath: a structural vs. catalytic function. *Journal of inorganic biochemistry*, 58(4), 235-244.
24. Ross, M. O., MacMillan, F., Wang, J., Nisthal, A., Lawton, T. J., Olafson, B. D., ... & Hoffman, B. M. (2019). Particulate methane monooxygenase contains only mononuclear copper centers. *Science*, 364(6440), 566-570.
25. Yoshizawa, K., & Shiota, Y. (2006). Conversion of methane to methanol at the mononuclear and dinuclear copper sites of particulate methane monooxygenase (pMMO): a DFT and QM/MM study. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 128(30), 9873-9881.
26. Sirajuddin, S., Barupala, D., Helling, S., Marcus, K., Stemmler, T. L., & Rosenzweig, A. C. (2014). Effects of zinc on particulate methane monooxygenase activity and structure. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 289(31), 21782-21794.
27. Ross, M. O., & Rosenzweig, A. C. (2017). A tale of two methane monooxygenases. *JBIC Journal of Biological Inorganic Chemistry*, 22, 307-319.
28. Lieberman, R. L., Shrestha, D. B., Doan, P. E., Hoffman, B. M., Stemmler, T. L., & Rosenzweig, A. C. (2003). Purified particulate methane monooxygenase from *Methylococcus capsulatus* (Bath) is a dimer with both mononuclear copper and a copper-containing cluster. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 100(7), 3820-3825.
29. Chan, S. I., Chen, K. H. C., Yu, S. S. F., Chen, C. L., & Kuo, S. S. J. (2004). Toward delineating the structure and function of the particulate methane monooxygenase from methanotrophic bacteria. *Biochemistry*, 43(15), 4421-4430.
30. Smith, T. J., & Dalton, H. (2004). Biocatalysis by methane monooxygenase and its implications for the petroleum industry. *Studies in surface science and catalysis*, 151, 177-192.
31. Choi, D. W., Kunz, R. C., Boyd, E. S., Semrau, J. D., Antholine, W. E., Han, J. I., ... &

- DiSpirito, A. A. (2003). The membrane-associated methane monooxygenase (pMMO) and pMMO-NADH: quinone oxidoreductase complex from *Methylococcus capsulatus* Bath. *Journal of bacteriology*, *185*(19), 5755-5764.
32. Cook, S. A., & Shiemke, A. K. (2002). Evidence that a type-2 NADH: quinone oxidoreductase mediates electron transfer to particulate methane monooxygenase in *Methylococcus capsulatus*. *Archives of biochemistry and biophysics*, *398*(1), 32-40.
33. Brynolf, S., Fridell, E., & Andersson, K. (2014). Environmental assessment of marine fuels: liquefied natural gas, liquefied biogas, methanol and bio-methanol. *Journal of cleaner production*, *74*, 86-95.
34. Choe, C., Byun, M., Lee, H., & Lim, H. (2022). Techno-economic and environmental assessments for sustainable bio-methanol production as landfill gas valorization. *Waste Management*, *150*, 90-97.
35. Zhang, Z., Delcroix, B., Rezazgui, O., & Mangin, P. (2021). Simulation and techno-economic assessment of bio-methanol production from pine biomass, biochar and pyrolysis oil. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, *44*, 101002.
36. Iaquaniello, G., Centi, G., Salladini, A., Palo, E., Perathoner, S., & Spadaccini, L. (2017). Waste-to-methanol: Process and economics assessment. *Bioresour. Technol.*, *243*, 611-619.
37. Hobson, C., & Márquez, C. (2018). Renewable methanol report. *Methanol Institute, Singapore*.